

Entropy as a Description of the Interactions in a System Part II?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 13, 2024

In Part I, we noted that for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas (which is really a distribution of energy problem with no bias, it seems), one may take a strictly global view and maximize entropy subject to an average energy constraint or, alternatively, consider local interactions and conservation of energy, with globally related probabilities $f(e_i)$. In such a case, conservation of energy $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$ removes bias because any e_i, e_j and e_k, e_l pairs are allowed, i.e. they are given the same weight. In the interaction view, one obtains a constant T which must be set by a global constraint which fixes the total energy of the system. Thus, our argument was that one does not necessarily need to think in terms of an entropy function which must be maximized subject to constraint. We gave the example of a quantum bound state.

Here we wish to revisit the idea of the interaction view which uses conservation of energy and compare it to the global entropy approach. We also wish to consider the quantum mechanical type of probabilities $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ (for a free particle) which are linked to conservation of energy and momentum and also remove bias. These probabilities remove bias and so are in keeping with the ideas of the Maxwell-Boltzmann interaction approach in a sense, but only apply to the local situation unlike the Maxwell-Boltzmann case which uses global $f(e_i)$ s.

We further note that a p in one direction implies a ruler gradation of \hbar/p , but one may consider p as a vector with an external set of axis and consider (p_x, p_y, p_z) with the ruler gradations, \hbar/p_x , \hbar/p_y , \hbar/p_z . We argue that these gradations allow for a removal of bias in each direction, but are associated with momentum conservation and not with the distribution of any global quantity.

In a Maxwell-Boltzmann problem, one may start with two body elastic scattering, but this is already linked to a global system because one uses $f(e_i)f(e_j)$, where f is probability, to describe the probability for an e_i, e_j collision to occur. Quantum mechanics, on the other hand, introduces the idea of conservation of energy and momentum at a local level (i.e. two particle scattering) using probabilities already incorporates the notion of bias removal, but at a strictly local level. Thus, we suggest that probabilities, $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$, should exist for this reason (if not for others) and do not in classical mechanics.

The Toss of a Die or Coin

Classically for the toss of a die or coin one may ask what is the probability for heads or tails or 1-6. If one has no information about the interaction processes (the toss or roll), one would guess equal probability for each result. This, however, requires many runs to manifest itself. One may have a single coin or die and toss or roll it many times. Equivalently, one may have many independent coins and dice which are being tossed or rolled at the same time. This leads to the idea of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. The gas has N particles and a total energy of E . If one knows nothing of the interactions, one may argue that any distribution of single particle energies over N particles such that the total is E carries the same weight, i.e. there is no reason for any bias.

This is a global approach and if one wishes to keep a only a global viewpoint, then one may introduce the idea of maximization of entropy subject to a constraint, i.e.

$$\text{Maximize } - \sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) + 1/T \sum_i e_i f(e_i) \quad ((1))$$

We argued in Part I, however, that physical scattering (two body) occurs and that the entropy approach was a mathematical equivalent which described the kind of interactions which take place. Here, we note that the entropy approach is a strictly global one, whereas the consideration of interactions is partly local, partly global.

Two Body Scattering

Given the notion of two body scattering in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, one may ask why interactions should be elastic. If they are not elastic, this means that one would need to establish a set of rules or constraints which show when energy is lost and when it is gained, because in the big picture (i.e. many 2-body scattering events) one cannot lose or gain energy. A set of constraints, however, is equivalent to bias and if one wishes the simplest picture without any bias, then one would eliminate these constraints and use conservation of energy in 2-body interactions.

At this point, a two body elastic interaction is local. The scenario becomes global if one considers that there are N independent particles and total energy E such that $f(e_i)$ exists. Then:

$$f(e_i)f(e_j) \text{ is the probability for } e_i \text{ and } e_j \text{ to scatter } ((2))$$

If energy is conserved, then one may still ask: Is there any bias in the final energies?
If there is bias, then one needs a set of rules to describe it. By removing bias, one uses:

$$e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l \text{ and } f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l) \quad ((3))$$

This then leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution by taking \ln of the second expression and equating it to $-1/T$ multiplied by the first. In other words, as argued in Part I, one does not need the idea of entropy and its maximization.

Not All Problems Are Solved by Maximizing Entropy Subject to Constraints

As argued above, the idea of maximizing entropy is linked with non-biased E distribution and so does not apply to all interaction situations. In Part I, we discussed the quantum bound case which has interactions and probabilities $\exp(ipx)$, but does not maximize entropy subject to a separate constraint because the interaction with $V(x)$ cannot be separated from the constant E_{ave} at each x point.

Here we consider $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ in more detail.

exp(ipx) and exp(-iEt)

In ((3)) for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, we used conservation of energy as an a priori idea which removed bias. Otherwise, rules for energy gain and loss in two body scattering would need to be introduced. The probability, however, which appeared in the discussion was $f(e_i)$ which is a global one linked to many particles in a gas.

We argue, however, that if one considers only two particles (i.e. a strictly local) situation, then one might expect conservation of energy and momentum for the same reason, a minimal amount of bias. If two particles collide and don't conserve energy then one needs extra rules to describe a loss of energy (maybe to noise, heat etc.). Thus, the simplest scenario is conservation of energy and momentum to remove bias and there should be local (not MB global) probabilities to describe this.

This then leads to: $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ so that:

$$\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad \text{and} \quad \exp(-iE_1t)\exp(-iE_2t) = \exp(-i(E_1+E_2)t) \quad ((4))$$

One may see that one may further remove bias by allowing for any $p_1+p_2 = p_3+p_4$ (one dimension) and $E_1+E_2=E_3+E_4$. This is completely consistent with the removal of bias in the Maxwell-Boltzmann 2-body scattering scheme, but exists at the local level only. It seems that such a local probability scheme is required, namely the scheme of quantum mechanics which is absent in classical mechanics. The idea of conservation of energy and momentum at a local level (i.e. two particle scattering) using probabilities already incorporates the notion of bias removal.

exp(ipx) versus exp(ipx x) exp(i py y) exp(i pz z)

One may note that $\exp(ipx)$ represents motion in a given x direction with a ruler gradation or spatial information of \hbar/p . All points within this gradation have the same probability or entropy. It is possible, however, to rotate the axes. In such a case, one has p_x, p_y, p_z . These represent physical components of impulse. For example, even though p may lie along a certain "x", a target may be oriented so that only a component of p hits it. In such a case, the p_x, p_y, p_z scheme must be used and $\exp(ipx x)$ with \hbar/p_x etc is used to describe conservation of momentum in this direction with $\exp(ip_y y)$ and $\exp(ip_z z)$ handling conservation of momentum in those directions. The point is that for $\exp(i p "x")$ one has \hbar/p while for (p_x, p_y, p_z) one has $\hbar/p_x, \hbar/p_y$ and \hbar/p_z . Thus, a single ruler gradation \hbar/p maps into three ruler gradations values. This suggests, we argue, that one does not look at information by itself in this scenario (i.e. single entropy function), but rather focuses on how $\exp(ipx x)$ etc is linked with conservation of momentum and a lack of bias in one direction. $\exp(i p_y x)$ and $\exp(ip_z z)$ are then examined separately.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the maximization of entropy subject to an energy constraint used in the Maxwell-Boltzmann gas scenario is a global approach to remove bias. Locally, however,

two body scattering occurs and physically one may try to remove bias at this level. Actually, two body scattering cannot be strictly local because even though one considers an e_i+e_j , there are many e_i and e_j in the gas and so one uses $f(e_i)$ and $f(e_j)$ probabilities to describe the global probability for an e_i and e_j to collide. We suggest that conservation of energy arises as the least biased scenario because otherwise constraints would need to be introduced to show when energy was lost and when it was gained for many two body scattering scenarios. By introducing conservation of energy, one actually removes bias by suggesting that $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$ and $f(e_i)f(e_j)=f(e_k)f(e_l)$. Thus, no entropy and no maximization of entropy is needed because all bias is removed.

We then note that the removal of bias seems to be linked with conservation. In a strictly local collision with energy and momentum conserved, one could have probabilities which remove all bias and at the same time are linked with these conservation laws. We suggest that this is exactly what the quantum free particle probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ do.